
IMPORTANCE OF TILLAGE IN VINEYARDS

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Annotation. At the end of harvesting, the aisles are loosened with the help of a PRVN-2.5A or PRVM-3 plow-ripper to a depth of 20-22 cm or more. This is necessary for better absorption of moisture into the soil, and most importantly, to facilitate and better cover the bushes for the winter. In the Sea of, autumn plowing on cohesive soils is carried out by 22-25 cm. In cases where the root system of the grapes is located close to the soil surface or it is not advisable to turn its deep layers up, they plow smaller. In arid conditions of the Azov region, 4-5 cultivations are usually enough.

Keywords: processing, soil, row spacing, loosening, vineyard, cultivation

Аннотация. По окончании уборки урожая междурядья рыхлят с помощью плуга-рыхлителя ПРВН-2.5А или ПРВМ-3 на глубину 20-22 см и более. Это необходимо для лучшего впитывания в почву влаги, а главное-для облегчения и более качественного проведения укрывки кустов на зиму. В Приазовье осеннюю вспашку на связных почвах проводят на 22-25 см. В тех случаях, когда корневая система винограда располагается близко от поверхности почвы или же нецелесообразно выворачивать ее глубокие слои наверх, пахут мельче. В засушливых условиях приазовья обычно достаточно 4-5 культивации.

Ключевые слова: обработка, почвы, междурядий, рыхления, виноградника, культивации

Introduction. Rational tillage is an indispensable condition for increasing the yield of grapes and improving its quality. It includes a system of techniques for influencing the soil, ensuring the creation of the most favorable conditions for plant growth in specific natural, organizational and economic conditions. The system of soil maintenance in vineyards should provide for the greatest accumulation and conservation of moisture in it, the creation of an optimal air regime, a constant increase in soil fertility, protection from water and wind erosion, the destruction of weeds and pests of the vine, the incorporation of organic and mineral fertilizers, covering the bushes for the winter and opening them in the spring with a covering culture.

In the arid conditions of the Karshi region, when cultivating grapes on stemless fan formations, tillage is reduced to its constant content in the state of black fallow. This is achieved by autumn and spring deep plowing of row-spacings with layer turnover, deep loosening without layer turnover (chiselling), spring-summer small cultivations in row-spacings and rows, deep loosening to renew the plantation, as well as the use of herbicides to kill weeds.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

At the end of harvesting, the aisles are loosened with the help of a PRVN-2.5A or PRVM-3 plow-ripper to a depth of 20-22 cm or more. This is necessary for better absorption of moisture into the soil, and most importantly, to facilitate and better cover the bushes for the winter. In vineyards with sandy and shelly-sandy soils, post-harvest loosening of row spacings should not be carried out in order to avoid blowing the soil out by strong winds. In late October-early November, autumn plowing of row-spacings is carried out, combining it with hilling bushes for the winter. It is impossible to plow heavily dried soil, and especially without post-harvest loosening, since in this case it is difficult to avoid large blocks that cannot be crushed. They increase the drying up of the soil and its freezing in winter, as a result of which the likelihood of damage to the bushes by winter frosts increases. Later covering of grapes is undesirable because in the Sea of starting from the second half of November, a period of prolonged rains begins. Too wet soil sticks to the working bodies of tillage machines, the quality of covering and the productivity of the units are reduced. It is very important to correctly set the depth of plowing, which depends on the type of soil, its moisture content and the agricultural technology used. In the Sea of autumn plowing on cohesive soils is carried out by 22-25 cm. In cases where the root system of the grapes is located close to the soil surface or it is not advisable to turn its deep layers up, they plow smaller.

After covering the bushes, row spacing should not be harrowed. The wavy surface of the vineyard absorbs autumn and winter precipitation better and resists water and wind erosion. The grapes are usually spudded in such a way that the head and sleeves of the bushes are covered, as well as 4-5 eyes from the base of annual shoots. At the same time, the earth from the row spacing must be taken evenly, and even better, at some distance from the head of the bush (50-60 cm) in order to avoid exposing the root system. For autumn plowing, simultaneously with earthing up bushes for the winter, PRVN-2.5A or PRVN-3 machines are used, aggregated with tractors T-54V, T-74, DT-75, DT-75M, T-4, etc.

Spring processing begins with the opening of the bushes. They start it as soon as the condition of the soil allows, which usually falls on the second or third decade of March, and in years with a long spring, at the beginning of April. Open the bushes in two stages. First, the covering shafts are partially plowed by machines

PRVN-2.5A or PRVM-3, in which the covering bodies are set to the "ploughing" position. This work is best done using the PRVN-74000 device, which results in the plowing of a much larger part of the covering shaft. When using it, it is necessary to ensure that the opening bodies are buried no more than 10-15 cm into the soil, and the disks have an angle of inclination forward and towards the shaft. It is advisable to combine the preliminary plowing of the covering shafts with the harrowing of the soil in one track, using two "zigzag" harrow links for this.

Finally, the covering shaft of the earth is removed by pneumatic machines of various designs. The PMM-2.5 machine completely opens the bushes in one pass along each row spacing. It is mounted on a machine PRVN-2.5A, equipped with fragmentary casings, two paired scraper sections and a high-pressure fan VVD-8. The fan drive is carried out from the power take-off shaft of the T-54V, DT-75, DT-75M tractors. The productivity of the unit is up to 0.68 ha/h. It is necessary to apply PMM-2.5 when the soil has already dried out relatively well. In vineyards with heavy soils, it is better to use the MPV-1 machine, whose productivity is up to 0.4 ha / h. It is impossible to allow delays with the beginning of the opening of the bushes, as this leads to a significant death of the eyes from damping out. After opening and pruning the bushes, it is very important to collect and free the aisles from vine trimmings in a timely manner. For this purpose, vine pickers LNV-1.5 and PVN-1.5A are used, which rake the trimmings into windrows and leave them on intercellular roads. Their productivity is greatly increased if the remote vine is dropped into the middle of the row spacing from two adjacent rows. From the intercellular roads, the windrows are pulled together by drags or they are loaded onto tractor trailers and taken out. The most rational utilization of cuttings is their simultaneous collection, grinding and deep incorporation into the soil in order to enrich them with organic matter. Special machines for this have already been created and will soon go into mass production. To improve soil aeration and weed control, chiselling is carried out with narrow-loosening paws to a depth of 20-25 cm, depending on the type of soil and the location of the root system of the bushes. By the time the buds open, spring work in the vineyard should be completed. In summer, row-spacing cultivation is carried out with simultaneous tillage in rows. This is necessary for weed control, accumulation and conservation of moisture. The amount of cultivation depends on meteorological conditions, the degree of development of weeds and soil type. In arid conditions of the Karshi region, 4-5 cultivations are usually enough. The last time the soil is cultivated at the beginning of the ripening of the grapes.

In the struggle for more complete moisture retention and energy savings, one should strive to reduce the number of treatments. Frequent loosening without regard to the state of the soil also leads to the destruction of its structure. On sandy and shell-sandy soils, excessive loosening often causes it to be blown out, as a result, the

root system of bushes is exposed, shoots, leaves and clusters are spotted with sand. If, for some reason, the soil was blown out in the vineyard and the roots were exposed, special techniques are used - sediment and backfill. To carry out the draft of the bush, carefully dig a hole on the side to expose the roots as much as possible. After that, the bush is lowered down, the roots are covered with sand, and covered with straw or reeds from above. Bedding is done in autumn or even winter. For this purpose, deep plowing of row-spacings is carried out and a layer of sand of 30-35 cm is added to the bushes. These techniques contribute to the rapid recovery of grape bushes. To avoid the formation of a compacted soil layer ("soles"), the first cultivation is carried out 12-15 cm, and subsequent ones - 1-2 cm smaller. Inter-row cultivation with tillage in rows is carried out by PRVN-2.5A or PRVM-3 machines equipped with PRVN-72000 and PRVM-11000 devices, respectively, but they can only be used on fruit-bearing vineyards, that is, not younger than three years. This is due to the fact that young plantations that do not have thickened perennial wood are easily cut at the base of the bush with knives of devices. For the same reason, in a vineyard where plantings have been repaired by replanting chibouks, seedlings or layering, wooden or metal pegs must be installed near each young plant. Most water enters the soil usually in the autumn-winter period. It is not uncommon for years when a significant proportion of the need for moisture in grape bushes is covered by autumn-winter precipitation. Therefore, measures for the accumulation and preservation of moisture should begin in the fall, after harvesting, and continue throughout the winter, until spring. In spring and summer, the main task of tillage is to preserve the moisture accumulated during the winter, as well as to accumulate and save the moisture of spring-summer precipitation.

The following system of agricultural practices best meets the listed tasks of soil cultivation in the conditions of the Karshi and Kitab regions:

- autumn loosening after harvesting and autumn digging in the rows;
- autumn plowing with simultaneous sheltering of bushes for the winter;
- the device of earth rollers-lintels;
- snow retention;
- early spring horse harrowing to cover moisture;
- spring plowing of covering shafts with sealing of detachable furrows in row spacing;
- spring loosening to create "mulch" and destroy compaction along the tractor track;
- Summer cultivation with hoeing in the ranks.

In addition to these annual agricultural practices, it is necessary to periodically deep loosen the soil in the aisles of vineyards - "plantage renewal".

The experience of the Institute of Viticulture and Advanced Farms shows that the use of such a tillage system in vineyards in combination with fertilizer, protective forest belts and the correct laying of vineyards helps to increase the yield of plantations by 25-35 percent. For the implementation of the system, appropriate means of mechanization of tillage are needed. Such a basic tool in viticulture is a universal machine brand VUM-60.

This machine is designed to work in row spacings of 2 and 2.5 meters in combination with a KD-35 tractor. All types of work are carried out by various working bodies that can be replaced. The permanent part of the machine is a trolley, consisting of a frame with a trailer, an axle with wheels and an automatic machine with a depth adjustment mechanism.

Two hanging frames are included for attaching the working bodies to the machine. One of them is used to work in the row spacing with a width of 2 meters, and the second, large, in the row spacing of 2.5 meters.

The machine is equipped with a set of working bodies for loosening the soil between rows to a depth of up to 60 centimeters in order to update the planting, cultivation (weeding) to a depth of 6-12 centimeters, loosening (chiseling) to a depth of 25 centimeters, autumn plowing with covering the vines, spring plowing in row-spacing with half-opening of bushes, digging of grapes: seedlings. Recently, the machine has been additionally equipped with special devices that make it possible to: cut irrigation furrows in irrigated vineyards, planting furrows in a grape nursery and sow fertilizers when renovating the plantation.

The VUM-60 machine can also be adapted for soil cultivation in a square-nested planting of grapes. The arrangement of devices for the indicated purposes and the methods of using the machine are described in detail in instructions for square nested grapes.

At present, the number of VUM-60 machines in state farms and MTS has increased significantly. This expands the possibilities of using the tillage system. Below are descriptions of its individual techniques.

The purpose of the reception is to loosen the soil that has compacted over the summer, to facilitate the accumulation of autumn precipitation, and to destroy the lumpiness. Deadline for work: September - early October, processing depth - 20-22 centimeters.

This operation, in addition to the agrotechnical significance indicated above, has a positive and even decisive effect on the quality and success of grape cover. due to the natural process of compaction, due to trampling it down during the harvesting period, as well as as a result of the development of weeds. The operation of a covering plow on such soil is accompanied by frequent stops from clogging with

weeds "high traction resistance, often unbearable for the KD-35 tractor, and poor quality of covering due to the coarseness of the soil.

Post-harvest loosening of the soil prevents the development of weeds and creates favorable conditions both for the plantations themselves and for high-quality and successful completion of the responsible operation of covering the vines for the winter. The performance of the unit at this job is 3.5-4.5 hectares per shift.

Simultaneously with autumn loosening, autumn digging of the soil in the rows of vineyards is also carried out. It is carried out everywhere by hand, with shovels, to a depth of 22-25 centimeters. It takes 16 man-days to dig rows per hectare.

This work is carried out after the autumn pruning of the bushes simultaneously with the covering of the vines for the winter with a tractor plow. Deadline: implementation: end of October - beginning of November.

Before covering, the sleeves of the bush are laid along the row on two sides and fixed in this position, lightly sprinkled with earth or pinned with hairpins. Experience shows that this work is easier to do together than alone; one of the workers holds the bush, slightly bending the sleeves, and the other presses them down with earth.

It usually takes 8 man-days to pre-lay the bushes and cover with earth, and to set the earth cover on the bushes after the passage of the plow-4.

Preparing a vineyard for machine covering is very time consuming. For the smooth operation of one unit, at least 40 people must be involved in laying the vines.

Following the pavers, a tractor with a covering plow passes and closes the bushes.

It should be noted that usually the land for digging: the vines are taken from one side of the row, as a result of which a strip of recesses is formed in the aisle on the side. If the wheel falls into these recesses, then the car gets a side roll. The working bodies located to this side go deeper than the others and, due to the asymmetry of the load, the machine blows in the direction of less resistance. At the same time, the stability of the machine is disturbed, and the quality of the covering is sharply reduced. Therefore, the land for digging the vines must be taken either directly from the bushes or in the middle of the aisle, but not where the wheels of the covering plow should pass.

When covering grapes, the covering plow is required to completely cover the laid vine with a layer of earth 15+5 centimeters thick. This is achieved by arranging the working bodies for row spacings of 2 and 2.5 meters according to the scheme shown in fig. 1.

Rice. 1. Completion of the VUM-60 machine for plowing with vine covering: at the top - in a row spacing of 2 meters, at the bottom - in a row spacing of 2.5 meters

It must be remembered that the mutual arrangement of bodies and the total width of the plow can vary in relation to local conditions. So, when covering young vineyards, the vines of which fit well on the soil surface, the total grip of the plow can be increased to 1600 millimeters. The depth of plowing in such vineyards of 15-16 centimeters is sufficient to form a covering shaft with reliable protection of the vines from freezing.

Under these conditions, the KD-35 tractor works with the plow in second gear. In vineyards where improper planting and formation of bushes have led to the fact that the heads of the bushes protrude above the soil surface, and the sleeves and vines do not lend themselves to more or less perfect laying, cover bodies should be placed further from the rows, and the plowing depth should be increased to 22-23 centimeters. In this regard, the load increases significantly and work with the KD-35 tractor becomes possible only in first gear.

In vineyards with row spacing of 2.5 meters on heavy soils, the KD-35 tractor replaces the DT-54 and STZ-NATI. But in row spacings of 2 meters, which are not passable for these tractors, work in especially difficult conditions has to be carried out on a double traction KD-35.

In order not to expose the bottom of the furrow following the traces of the working bodies processing the middle of the aisle, it is recommended to remove the blades and replace them with overlays BM-4033, 4034, 4035 and 4036, attached to the machine.

When the plow is working with overlays instead of moldboards, the sole from these working bodies in the row-spacing remains covered with a layer of soil, which protects the roots of the grapes from freezing. Productivity VUM-60 on covering -

3.5-4.25 hectares per shift. In areas where, due to the conditions of the relief, tractor processing is impossible, autumn plowing is carried out with horse plows after covering the bushes. If the vineyard is cultivated by hand, instead of plowing in the autumn, they carry out continuous digging, also after covering the bushes. About 40 man-days are required to carry out this work per hectare.

The device of earthen rollers-lintels. Autumn plowing is still not able to completely protect vine plantations from useless moisture loss in the autumn-winter period in those areas where the wrong direction of the rows was made during planting - along the slopes. Here, special measures are required to retain autumn precipitation and melt water. These measures consist in the fact that in the fall, after the shelter of the vineyards, in the aisles (between the covering shafts), transverse earthen rollers-lintels are arranged. With a small slope of the surface of the site, the rollers are usually placed every 20 meters. If the surface is more sloping, the distances between the jumpers are reduced accordingly. The aisles of vineyards are thus broken up by rollers into a number of closed sections, in which melt water is retained and gradually absorbed into the soil.

Transverse earthen rollers are arranged using a wooden horse-drawn engine or manually with shovels. In the latter case, 2-3 man-days are required per hectare. Completion date is the second half of November. The main task of spring-summer cultivation in vineyards is to prevent the useless loss of autumn-winter water reserves by soil through evaporation, as well as to accumulate and conserve moisture from spring-summer precipitation. With the onset of spring, it is first of all necessary to quickly close the moisture in the soil. To do this, in the vineyards in early spring (late March - early April), especially in the case of a delay in opening the bushes, fine loosening of the soil surface is carried out. It should be carried out only with mounted light tools (harrows) and completed as soon as possible - 2-3 days. A worker with one horse is able to do this work in a day on an area of about 4 hectares.

The purpose of the reception is to facilitate the spring opening of vine bushes, as well as to partially close up the detachable furrows in the aisles formed by the VUM-60 machine when sheltering the bushes for the winter.

The essence of the operation lies in the fact that the bulk of the soil from the rows, where it was displaced by the plow when covering the vines, is moved to the middle of the row spacing and furrows are made along the rows to lay the soil remaining in the covering shafts in them. This work is performed by the VUM-60 machine with the arrangement of working bodies according to Fig. 2.

Rice. 2. The position of the bodies on the VUM-60 frame for half-opening the vines in row spacing of 2.5 meters

When preparing the VUM-60 machine for work on plowing, it is necessary to install working bodies with the largest grip, which makes it possible to work without damaging the bushes. On flat areas with fairly straight rows and with small (+5 centimeters) deviations in row spacing, it is possible to work with a grip of 1.9-1.8 meters - in row spacings of 2.5 meters and with a grip of 1.5 meters - in two-meter row spacings. Half-opening is carried out simultaneously with harrowing in one track. In vineyards with a row spacing of 2.5 meters, two links of a zigzag harrow are used for this purpose, with their attachment to the VUM-60 machine by means of a conventional paired swath on an extended link.

DISCUSSION

To work in two-meter row spacing, two links are also required, but each of them must be cut into one zigzag bar. Two truncated links give a total capture of one and a half harrows - 1.35 meters. In both cases, the links are interconnected by a chain.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The paired swath for shortened harrows must also be shortened with a corresponding relocation of the attachment points. The productivity of the VUM-60 at this job is 4.25-4.75 hectares per shift. Deadline for work: beginning of April, sometimes - the end of March.

It should be borne in mind that the furrows created during spring plowing along the rows of the vineyard contribute to a noticeable loss of soil moisture. In order to prevent this phenomenon, it is necessary to strive to reduce the gap between the plowing of covering shafts and the subsequent manual opening of grape bushes.

Conclusion. In arid regions, it is especially dangerous to leave open furrows after plowing the covering shaft for a long time. Therefore, here it is necessary to

organize the work in such a way that the production team has time to manually open the grapes after the tractor.

The bushes are opened during plowing as follows: they rake the earth from the covered vines with hoes, trying not to damage them. After that, the sleeves of the bush are carefully lifted with a pitchfork and finally freed from the ground. The soil under the bushes is leveled, dropping it into the furrows made by the plow.

It is convenient to open vineyards in groups of 2 people. Each of them rakes the earth from under the bush into the furrow of its aisle.

The productivity of manual labor in opening vine bushes after plowing a covering shaft is on average 0.08-0.10 hectares per person per day, and labor costs are 10-12 man-days per hectare.

Collective and state farms often refuse to cover young bushes with a tractor plow and do it by hand. Such a decision is quite reasonable.

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